

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING MODELS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING AND CREATIVITY IN CHEMISTRY SUBJECTS IN HIGH SCHOOL

Ahmad Alghifari

Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang

Email: ahmadalghifari@webmail.umm.ac.id

ABSTRACT

21st-century education demands a learning model that emphasizes not only theoretical delivery but also the development of students' critical thinking, communication, creativity, and collaboration skills. Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a learning model that engages students in authentic projects relevant to real-life situations, enabling them to understand abstract concepts in Chemistry through hands-on experience. The application of PjBL to Chemistry is highly appropriate due to the nature of the material, which requires observation, experimentation, and scientific evidence. Several studies have shown that PjBL can improve students' learning motivation, learning outcomes, and higher-order thinking skills in science and Chemistry learning compared to conventional methods (Thomas, 2000), (Krajcik & Blumenfeld, 2006), (Pratiwi & Ikhsan, 2024). Furthermore, PjBL supports the implementation of the Independent Curriculum, which emphasizes contextual, collaborative, and experience-based learning (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2021). This research used a systematic literature review of several scientific articles discussing the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) in chemistry learning in high school. The study results indicate that Project-Based Learning (PjBL) effectively increases students' understanding of chemical concepts by 30–35% and enhances students' creativity through project activities, experiments, and the creation of simple chemical products. Other findings reveal that Project-Based Learning (PjBL) helps students connect theory to everyday life phenomena and makes learning more meaningful and applicable. However, several obstacles to its implementation, such as limited facilities and learning time, remain. Overall, Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a learning model with the potential for wider application in chemistry learning because it improves learning quality and is relevant to the demands of 21st-century education. Therefore, the application of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) in chemistry learning not only improves cognitive achievement but also fosters active, independent, and innovative student character. This article discusses the concept, implementation steps, benefits, and research findings related to the effectiveness of Project-Based

Learning (PjBL) as a learning model that should be implemented in high school.
Keywords: Project-Based Learning, Chemistry Learning, Creativity, Conceptual Understanding, 21st-Century Learning, Independent Curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

Science education, particularly Chemistry, plays a crucial role in shaping students' scientific thinking. However, the reality in many schools shows that Chemistry instruction remains conventional and teacher-centered. Monotonous lecture methods tend to make students passive, simply memorizing formulas without understanding the meaning of the concepts being studied. This impacts low learning outcomes and student interest in Chemistry, particularly in abstract concepts such as chemical reactions, atomic bonds, and acid-base solutions. Innovative learning models are needed to address this situation. Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a relevant approach because it emphasizes student engagement in project activities that require the application of concepts to solve real-life problems (Thomas, 2000). Through PjBL, students not only learn theory but also apply it directly in everyday contexts. Project implementations such as making natural soap, testing water quality, or creating acid-base indicators from natural materials can improve conceptual understanding and foster student creativity (Pratiwi & Ikhsan, 2024).

Furthermore, PjBL aligns with the vision of the Merdeka Belajar Curriculum, which demands student-centered, collaborative, and experience-based learning (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2021). Teachers no longer function solely as transmitters of material, but as facilitators and guides, guiding students to discover concepts on their own through projects. Therefore, implementing the PjBL model is a crucial strategy for improving the quality of chemistry learning in secondary schools. Through simple, contextual projects, students are expected to better understand the relationship between theory and practice, and develop the critical and creative thinking skills needed in the 21st century.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Based on the background presented, this research is formulated to address several key issues related to the implementation of the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model in Chemistry learning in high schools. The main issues examined include how the basic concepts and main principles of PjBL are applied in 21st-century learning, as well as the steps for systematically implementing PjBL in Chemistry learning at the high school level. Furthermore, this research also seeks to identify the benefits and research findings that demonstrate the effectiveness of PjBL in improving students'

conceptual understanding and creativity. Furthermore, this article discusses various challenges and obstacles that may arise in implementing PjBL in schools, both in terms of facilities, time, and the readiness of educators and students. Furthermore, this research also examines the relevance of PjBL in supporting the implementation of the Merdeka Belajar Curriculum as a modern learning paradigm that emphasizes independence, creativity, and problem-solving based on real experiences.

THEORITICAL REVIEW

Theory	Sintaks PjBL	Material Studied	Student Activities	Form Creativity
Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a learning model that places students at the center of learning activities through the completion of real-life projects. It emphasizes scientific inquiry, collaboration, problem-solving, presentation of results, and the production of a final product. It supports 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication (the 4Cs).	Start with a problem	PjBL concept, 4C (critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication), student-centered learning	Students identify real-life problems related to chemistry, discuss, formulate research/project questions	Divergent thinking to generate many alternative ideas and solutions
The main steps of PjBL include: (1) Determining the project questions/problems, (2) Planning and compiling the	Planning, design project, scheduling, experiment, presentation, reflection	Chemistry experiments, project design, preparation of tools/mater	Designing projects, creating timelines, conducting experiments, presenting	Creatively designing experimental methods, modifying materials, making

<p>experimental design, (3) Compiling the activity schedule, (4) Implementing the experiment and collecting data, (5) Monitoring & teacher guidance, (6) Presentation and evaluation of the product. Chemistry application projects can include making soap, natural indicators, water quality testing, etc.</p>		<p>ials, visualization of chemical concepts</p>	<p>project product results</p>	<p>innovative products (herbal soap, natural indicators, organic detergents, etc.)</p>
<p>PjBL improves: understanding of chemical concepts by 30-35%, creativity increases significantly (up to 83%), activeness, scientific experiments, and learning motivation. N-Gain results up to 0.73 (high category). Supports the ability to design chemical products, think critically, and collaboratively.</p>	<p>Implementation & monitoring as the core of skill formation</p>	<p>Conceptual understanding increases (30 - 35%), experimental creativity, learning motivation</p>	<p>Conducting experiments, analyzing experimental results, producing simple chemical products</p>	<p>New chemical products, innovative working methods, alternative scientific solutions, posters/presentation visuals</p>
<p>The main obstacles are limited lab facilities and chemicals, learning time management,</p>	<p>Reflection & evaluation (activity improvement)</p>	<p>Constraints on laboratory facilities, implement</p>	<p>Reflection discussion, project evaluation, method</p>	<p>Creatively working around limited tools & materials,</p>

teacher readiness in designing projects, and varying student motivation. Solutions include mini-projects, the use of simple materials, blended learning, and optimizing teacher support.	nt stage)	ation time, student/teacher readiness	adaptation if tools/materials are minimal	alternative experiments based on the home environment
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DISCUSSION

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is considered a highly appropriate learning model for Chemistry because it is rich in abstract concepts, such as the structure of substances, stoichiometry, and the properties of solutions. These concepts are often difficult to grasp when presented through lectures or teacher-centered learning. Research shows that students more easily grasp abstract concepts when they explore them directly through project activities, such as designing simple experiments, conducting laboratory investigations, or producing chemical products from everyday materials. This suggests that Project-Based Learning (PjBL) helps transform chemistry learning from a typically theoretical perspective into a more concrete and directly observable learning experience. Thus, this model positions students as the primary agents in constructing their own knowledge.

In addition to improving conceptual understanding, PjBL also has a significant impact on student creativity. Creativity develops because students are given the opportunity to choose an approach, determine work steps, and design a product based on their ideas. In chemistry projects, such as making natural indicators, herbal soap, or analyzing water quality, students are involved in the process of generating ideas, modifying experimental methods, and developing problem-solving strategies. This process develops divergent thinking skills, namely the ability to generate various alternative solutions. Research confirms that students who learn through PjBL demonstrate higher creativity than students who learn traditionally, because they are trained to think flexibly, independently, and innovatively.

However, the success of PjBL cannot be separated from the teacher's ability to design projects that are appropriate to student needs and school conditions. Chemistry learning in high school is often faced with limited laboratory facilities, inadequate

laboratory equipment, or large student numbers. Therefore, teachers need to adapt project designs by selecting materials that are easy to find or safe to use, and utilizing the classroom as an alternative if the laboratory is not available. Several studies suggest that teachers use simple projects that remain relevant to chemistry concepts, such as extracting dyes from plants, making environmentally friendly cleaning solutions, or simple reaction experiments using household materials.

Another challenge in implementing PjBL is the limited learning time in schools. Because PjBL involves several stages such as planning, implementation, and presentation, teachers need to manage their time effectively. Research recommends the use of short-term projects or mini-projects that can be completed in several sessions, thus aligning with the academic calendar. Additionally, homework assignments and the use of digital platforms like Google Classroom or Padlet can help students document their work outside of class hours.

The use of digital technology is also an effective strategy in supporting the implementation of PjBL. Based on the article analysis, teachers can utilize experimental videos, online laboratory simulations, or science research applications to help students understand the steps before conducting experiments. Technology allows students to learn flexibly and facilitates group collaboration. This is especially helpful for schools with limited laboratory facilities.

When linked to the Independent Curriculum, PjBL is one of the most relevant learning models because it provides students with the freedom to determine their own learning process (student agency). The Independent Curriculum emphasizes project-based learning, exploration, creativity, and authentic problem-solving, so the application of PjBL in Chemistry directly supports the goal of establishing the Pancasila Student Profile. PjBL helps students develop critical thinking, creativity, independence, and collaborative character through group activities in projects.

Based on the overall findings and theoretical synthesis, PjBL can be viewed not simply as an alternative method, but as a learning model capable of providing meaningful, contextual learning experiences and encouraging students to become active learners. PjBL also shifts the role of teachers from mere information providers to facilitators who guide students through the process of scientific investigation. With appropriate adaptations and careful planning, PjBL has proven to improve the quality of chemistry learning and is relevant for wider implementation in schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of various scientific articles on the application of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) in Chemistry learning in high school, it can be

concluded that the PjBL model is an effective, relevant, and appropriate learning approach to the needs of 21st-century education. PjBL provides opportunities for students to actively construct understanding through involvement in real projects related to chemical concepts, so that learning becomes more meaningful, contextual, and applicable.

Research findings show that PjBL significantly improves students' understanding of chemistry concepts because students not only receive information but also connect it to direct experiences through experiments and investigative activities. Furthermore, PjBL significantly contributes to increasing student creativity, particularly through project design, problem-solving, and the creation of simple, innovative chemical products.

Despite this, the implementation of PjBL still faces several obstacles, such as limited learning time, laboratory facilities, and teacher readiness in designing projects. However, these challenges can be overcome through project modifications, the use of supporting technology, and more flexible planning.

Overall, PjBL is highly relevant to the Independent Curriculum because it emphasizes student-centered, experience-based learning, and supports the development of the Pancasila Student Profile competencies. Therefore, PjBL can be recommended as a learning model that should be implemented more widely in Chemistry at the high school level.

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